

Gaia BP/RP spectra classification through Self-Organizing Maps

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It was in the third data release of the Gaia mission when the gathered spectra were published for the first time. It was made a huge effort to extract astrophysical information from the low-resolution spectra (BP/RP), such as effective temperature, metallicity or the type of sources that were being analysed. However, some of the sources could not be correctly classified and the Outlier Analysis working package grouped them in a Self-Organizing map by just taking into account their spectra. Due to their promising results, we wanted to go one step further by trying to classify the BP/RP spectra of the sources following a similar and unsupervised approach. In this work, we are introducing a spectral classification approach where we build our models in an unsupervised way through Self-Organizing Maps which can be scaled to any number of sources to be processed.

1 Introduction

The Gaia Space Telescope [1] is one of the most ambitious missions of the European Space Agency (ESA) by creating the largest 3D map of the Milky Way gathering proper motions, astrometry values and spectra, among others. It was in the 3rd data release (GDR3) when both the RVS (high resolution) and BP/RP (low resolution) spectra came to light for the first time, publishing 1 million and 219 million spectra respectively.

Our research group takes part in the Outlier Analysis (OA) working package from Gaia [2], where it is performed data-clustering through Self-Organizing Maps (SOM) [3, 4] to group BP/RP spectra (only taking into account the flux) which is considered to be anomalous by other working packages. On the one hand, it is possible to group sources with similar spectra and assign them a spectral type if they are significant enough, and, on the other, to identify singular spectra which were not observed before. It was in GDR3 when the first OA results were published, where around 56 million BP/RP spectra were pro-

cessed. As a result, it was detected that more than 50% of such sources could be characterised, being able to assign them a spectral type.

Following the approach which was used in OA and taking into account the wonderful results achieved in GDR3 even analysing outlier sources, in the current research we want to go one step further by adapting the approach followed in OA with SOM Maps to classify the complete BP/RP survey.

2 Algorithm

As it was previously stated, in GDR3 219 million BP/RP spectra were published. Moreover, it is expected for this number to increase exponentially in the next data release. Even though the SOM algorithm we are following in OA is an improved version that can speed the training time up to 60% [4], it might not be feasible to follow this approach at Gaia's processing centre. For such reason, we decided to make an enhanced version to classify BP/RP spectra where we create several artificial intelligence (AI) models based on SOM Maps to classify the sources.

We decided to go on using SOM Maps rather than a semi-supervised or a fully supervised approach for two main reasons; to keep the essence of classifying the sources just by taking into account their spectra and not to replicate the behaviour of other working packages that use auxiliary data such as parallax or colour. For example, the Discrete Source Classifier (DSC) working package [2], with which we will compare our outcomes, performs a probabilistic classification of the sources by using more than one classifier. One of them uses only spectra data (in a supervised way), but the other one uses eight different features from Gaia, such as parallax or the G-magnitude [2].

The main advantage of using SOM maps is that the topological order of the training data is preserved. This means that similar spectra at the input are grouped into the same or a similar neuron. We can

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reach this state through the neuron prototype, which is the average representation of all the current sources contained in such a neuron. At each iteration of the training process, each spectrum is compared against the prototypes and the winning neuron where it is placed will be the one where the distance to the prototype is lower. The weight of the prototype is updated at the end of each iteration.

2.1 Data models

For performing classification we are using three different models based on SOM Maps. It was decided to segregate the data due to the amount of data available for each of the spectral types we are dealing with, as almost the survey is made up of stars. If we grouped the whole training set in one single map, we are taking the risk that the less representative types do not make up a neuron reflecting their morphology correctly. The maps that are being used and the data sources are explained below:

- **Stars map** We have two main sources of information. On the one hand, we obtain the main stellar types from an HR diagram and, on the other, from well-characterised Gaia sources.

The sources under the HR diagram are obtained from a low extinction HR diagram using Gaia data [5]. We based our data in the GDR2 paper that deals with HR diagrams [5], but applying the selection query to DR3. As a result, we obtained 17 million sources. Since the amount of data that can be used is enormous, we removed the sources that lay on low-populated areas and, on the other hand, we removed those spectra which are very similar. This is done both to speed up the training phase of the map and to get rid of spurious and redundant data, respectively.

Even though we can compute if a given star is located at the main sequence or at the giants branch, which we did at [6], due to the low resolution of BP/RP it is very difficult to distinguish both cases if we do not take into account at the training phase other parameters such as the luminosity of the star.

Moreover, we used Carbon Stars, Emission Line Stars and Ultra Cool stars retrieved from well-known sources used at Gaia. These can be obtained from the Gaia data archive.

- **Galaxies map** The training sources were given by Gaia experts who are working with galaxies, who used as a baseline [SDSSDR17](#). From the matching sources, they filtered out those with low-quality

taking into account the errors in redshift and magnitude.

- **Quasars map** It is composed of high quality sources from Sloan [SDSSDR16Q](#). Apart from having a Gaia identifier, we selected those sources with $z < 4.5$, with the quality flag $IS_QSO_FINAL = 1$. Moreover, we removed the fainter sources to have a cleaner dataset.

For performing classification with these models, it is necessary to compute beforehand, for each neuron, its *prototype spectrum* and its *threshold value*. As already explained, the former is a “synthetic” spectrum, representing the average spectrum shape of all the sources contained in the neuron. The latter represents the maximum distance to determine whether a source is an outlier or not. In order to know if a source is an outlier for a neuron, it is computed the source-prototype distance (d_{s-p}) and, afterwards; checked against the threshold value. That is, if $d_{s-p} > threshold$, then the source will be an outlier.

2.2 Classification algorithm

For the sources to be classified, we need two inputs; the spectra and the identifier of the source (for easily tracking the results). The process is done as follows:

1. **Traverse each map.** In this step, it is determined, for each map, the neuron where the source fits the best. For such, it is chosen the neuron where the distance to the prototype (d_{s-p}) is the lowest; $min(d_{s-p})$.
2. **Sort the neuron_map-source distances.** In the previous step, we took the best neuron-source distance for each map. Now, we are sorting these values in order to know the map where it fits the best.
3. **Determine if the source is an outlier.** As previously stated, each neuron contains a maximum threshold value which determines whether a source fits in the neuron, and thus, in the map (as a source is associated with the neuron where it fits the best).

If, for the map where it fits the best (determined at the previous step), $d_{s-p} > threshold$; the source will be marked as an outlier and its label will be “outlier”. Otherwise, the source will be associated with the map where it fits the best and the label will be inherited from the spectral type of the best-matching neuron.

3 Results

The classification tests introduced in this paper were done with the Gaia’s internally calibrated spectra in the same way as we do in the OA working package, using the 219 million spectra that were published in GDR3. Even though the given results are expressed in general terms of stars, galaxies and quasars, in our algorithm we give around 20 different spectral types.

The time required to perform the classification was 230 minutes in a machine with an Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2630 processor, 512 GB of RAM and 32 processors. Having such a number of processors allows to perform the source-by-source classification in parallel, implementing our algorithm in Java. The results of the execution are reflected in Table 1.

Source Type	Number of Sources	Percentage
Star	207070870	94.8 %
Galaxy	5873544	2.7%
Quasar	5505582	2.4%
Outlier	139	0.1%

Table 1: Sources classification statistics for the current work

In DR3, the DSC package provided both the sources classification and outlier detector for BP/RP spectra.

Comparing both results, we get quite similar results and can even give a spectral-type classification of some of their outliers (most of them as stars):

Figure 1: Confusion matrix between DSC and our work

On the other hand, we can also compare our results against the OA module. As you can see in Figure 2, the results are not as accurate as the ones obtained against DSC, since, in the case of quasars, there is a huge confusion between galaxies and quasars.

In this case, it will be necessary to make a further analysis of the mismatching sources to tune our algorithms.

Figure 2: Confusion matrix between OA and our work

4 Discussion

It is expected for the Gaia Mission to publish around 2 billion BP/RP spectra, which can be a difficult task for astronomers to explore such an amount of data, both in terms of time and computation. In the current work, we are introducing a new way to group such data, which can be useful to investigate the astrophysical properties of sources which are similar in terms of their morphology.

As it was demonstrated, this is a scalable method, since it took 4 hours in a machine with 32 cores to process the DR3 spectra. Even though for DR4 this number could grow exponentially, the algorithm can run either in a more powerful machine or in a cluster of machines to get the results even faster.

Despite being a recently developed approach to dealing with BP/RP spectra, the achieved results are quite consistent against the available methods. In fact, it is able to correctly classify sources which were initially considered to be outliers. The only exception appears with the sources that were classified by OA as quasars, which should be studied in more detail by refining the current models. Nonetheless, once one of the models is refined, it is straightforward to integrate it with the other ones and repeat the classification step.

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